

ACINO

Application-Centric IP/optical
Network Orchestration

ACINO / D6.3

First year report on dissemination and communication activities

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Summary

This ACINO deliverable D6.3 presents the communication and dissemination activities performed by the ACINO consortium during the first year of the project. The consortium has developed communication instruments to support such activities for the duration of the project:

- A graphical profile has been developed for ACINO, as well as document models for reports and presentations;
- A web site has been set up, describing the project, the challenges we are looking at, and our approach to solve them;
- A Twitter account has been set up to ensure presence in the social media and to allow a more dynamic communication;
- A fact sheet and a flyer have been developed.

The project has also held two further communication actions: a press release and an interview in a magazine.

The dissemination activities have been based on the participation in public events where the goals and concepts of ACINO were presented via publications, presentation, workshops, courses and demonstrations.

Overall, fifteen different dissemination activities have been performed:

- Four articles were published in conferences: at ICTON, ECOC and Photonics in Switching;
- Four presentations were held at conferences: at EUCNC, the OSA Advanced Photonics Conference, CTTE and OFC;
- The project participated to the organization of the Workshop on Network Function Virtualization and Programmable Networks at EUCNC;
- A tutorial entitled “Control Architectures for Multi-layer Networking: Distributed, centralized, or something in between?” was held at OFC;
- A course entitled “SC411: Multi-layer Interaction in the Age of Agile Optical Networking” was held at OFC;
- Three booths were held at OFC, ONS and the SDN & OpenFlow World Congress, where demonstrations were run;
- The project started contributing back to the Open Source Software community maintaining the Netphony controller.

Contacts have also been taken with several Open Source Software communities and European projects for future collaboration.

Finally, the project has devised detailed plans for its dissemination activities for the coming year.

1 Dissemination and communication strategy

This document is laid out as follows:

- This section presents our communication and dissemination strategy;
- Section 2 “Communication activities” discusses the tools that the project has created to help present ACINO’s concepts, ideas and activities: branding (with the creation of a logo and document models), tools to support the project’s dissemination activities (fact sheet, flyer), tools to reach out to the scientific community in a broad sense, using internet (website and Twitter account). It also lists the communication events (press releases, interviews) that have happened during this past year;
- Section 3 “Dissemination activities” presents the project’s interaction with its peers in scientific forums such as conferences and workshops;
- Section 4 “Participation in open Source Software communities” presents the project’s interaction with Open Source projects relevant for ACINO;
- Section 5 “Planned activities for the second year” provides a view of what is laying ahead of the project for its second year of activity: possible workshops, publications, participation in conferences and other events, and contacts with other projects and forums.
- Finally, Section 6 concludes on ACINO’s dissemination and communication activities for its first year.

The consortium strategy is to present the project goals to its selected target audience, in order to interact with it and discuss the challenges and possible solutions that ACINO is proposing, formulate adequate messages that will be delivered in the appropriate forums and disseminate the project results and achievements in the most appropriate venues. So the key words of our strategy, summarized in Figure 1, are **goals**, **target audience**, **messages**, **forums** and **instruments**. These are properly detailed in the following sub-sections.

Figure 1: Summary of the ACINO dissemination and communication strategy.

1.1 Goals

There are three main goals to our strategy:

- The first goal is the technical one, which is set forth in the project Grant Agreement, has evolved during the first year of activities and will be reported in the management and technical deliverables of ACINO.
- The second goal is to demonstrate the usefulness of the research carried out in the project.
- The third goal is to make the project and our activities visible, so that the consortium partners can interact with their peers, inform their target audiences about the project goals and challenges, and create opportunities to turn research results into added value.

1.2 Targets

The target groups that the consortium wants to interact with are both academic and industrial. On the academic side, the project plans to contribute back to the SDN state of the art with ACINO's concepts and research results through publications, workshops and similar events, and by targeted collaborations with other research and OSS groups. ACINO's collaboration with Open Source Software (OSS) groups will lead to the contribution of source code to these OSS communities.

On the industrial side, the project will interact with network equipment manufacturers and support some of their equipment in the solutions and demonstrations that are developed. In addition, it is expected that such as hardware vendors and implementers of SDN solutions will show an interest for ACINO.

Our main targets for the dissemination of the project results are:

- Academia, as we wish to contribute to the evolution of SDN using the concepts developed in ACINO;
- Standardization bodies: one of the consortium goals is to contribute to the improvement of existing standards related to IP and optical networking, if the opportunity arises;
- Open Source Community: the consortium will be using existing OSS software and plans to provide back improvements, bug fixes and new features;
- End users and customers: when disseminating project results, the consortium is addressing
 - Vendors and implementers of SDN solutions (developers of hardware or controllers, service/maintenance providers);
 - Network operators that can be considering SDN-based solutions for their next investments.

1.3 Messages

The message carried by our communication has to be tailored for each group that we are addressing:

- To the academia, our main focus should be to put forward our results that are relevant to various research groups;
- When targeting standards, our aim should be to propose improvements to existing ones, or to point out weaknesses and to propose corrective measures;
- With regards to OSS, communicating in advance about our goals and keeping in regular contact (both in terms of communication and with regular code updates) will be critical to receive acceptance within the targeted communities and to ensure that the code we contribute is maintained;
- Concerning end users and customers, our aim should be to highlight the benefits of the ACINO architecture compared to other network control systems, while taking care that the solutions we propose are not too disruptive and can integrate well with existing systems.

1.4 Forums

To foster the exchange of ideas about Software-Defined Networks and the solutions proposed by ACINO to orchestrate such networks, our strategy is to use Internet-based media as well as face-to-face meetings with our peers. For communication purposes, we have set up a website that provides not just a static description of what ACINO is, but that get dynamically updated with new content. We also use Twitter to promote and inform about the project, our activities and SDN at large.

Concerning dissemination activities and face-to-face meetings, we plan that the publication of papers in reviewed journals, our presence at conferences and the organization of workshops will give us the opportunity to interact with our peers, make new contacts, share ideas and possibly produce common research results with other groups.

1.5 Material

To support the consortium communication and dissemination effort, some generic tools have been developed:

- Internet-based tools to provide us efficient communication means: we have set up a website and a Twitter account;
- A digital profile, which allows us to create branding for the project, creating recognition as we communicate more;
- Some paper-based material (e.g. flyers) to communicate in the more traditional way.

Other material has and will continue being developed, as the project creates new results. These communication and dissemination results are the main subject of this deliverable. A non-exhaustive list is:

- Publications in journals and conferences;
- Presentations in conferences and workshops;
- Participations to events such as workshops and conferences;
- Demonstration of project results, at conferences or other events;
- Publication of open source software.

2 Communication activities

The consortium's communication activities have been divided into two parts: we have developed generic communication instruments that will be used for the duration of the project and we have debated with our target audience about ACINO in specific forums, when opportunities arose.

2.1 Communication instruments

To support our communication activities, the consortium has design a graphical profile for the project that is used in all our official communication. Since the project name, ACINO, means *grape* in Italian, the project them is inspired by this fruit. We have also produced a number of tools and communication means that we will use throughout the project. Furthermore, we have created document models, which are shown in the next subsection.

The project uses Internet-based communication to reach out to other researchers, the telecommunication community as well as the broader public. To do so, we have created a website, described in the second subsection, which allows us to present the project goals and partners in a verbose manner. For more ephemeral news and events, we have also opened a twitter account (see third subsection), as it allows more dynamic messaging. We use these last two tools to communicate about ACINO. Naturally, both sites use the ACINO graphical profile to create a recognizable branding of the project.

We have also designed generic documents, a flyer and a fact sheet, that describe the project, carry its messages and can be reused in the various forums that we participate in They are presented in the last subsection.

2.1.1 Document models

We have designed document models that use the project graphical profile for our reports and presentations, and are used for our official communication. The first pages are shown in Figure 2. These documents models are used for ACINO's official communication: public and private reporting about the project, presentations at conferences and other events. The models have been improved during the first year according to the feedback received by the consortium partners.

Figure 2 : Pictures of the first pages of the templates for the text (left) and presentation (right) documents.

2.1.2 Website

2.1.2.1 Site content

To promote the project, a web site [ACIWEB] with a clear interface has been developed. Naturally, the web site uses the graphical profile of the project. On the front page, shown in Figure 3, a top row gives access to facts about the project: the challenges faced and our approach to solve them.

The lower part of the main page presents external data about ACINO and is updated dynamically:

- The **News** section is automatically updated with the title of the five latest news articles that project members have written. The news are short articles related to project activities, our past presence at conferences, or where we point out articles about application-centric networking, SDN, IP/Optical orchestration, and other matters of interest for ACINO. The news area of the website can be accessed from the menu for an exhaustive list of the news articles.
- A **Meet us at** section lists upcoming events that ACINO members will be present at.
- A **Social** section lists the tweets from the ACINO account. This section is also automatically updated when new tweets are published, allowing minimal maintenance.

The website also contains a presentation of the project as well as other facts accessible through the menu.

Figure 3: Front page of the project website, located at www.acino.eu.

2.1.2.2 Site statistics

The site was up and running in March 2015, as early as the second month of the project, and we started gathering statistics on May 27th, 2015). Some key characteristics concerning the number of visits include:

- 3400+ sessions were created by a total of over 3000 visitors;
- Most visits to the site were by new visitors (less than 10% of the visitors were returning visitors);
- The site provided over 4300 page views;
- The bounce rate was around 85%, meaning that for 85% of the connections user looked only at the main page and did not request another page.

In terms of demographics, it is interesting to see that the site caught interest in many countries outside of Europe, as shown in Figure 4: in North America (USA and Canada), South America (in particular Brazil,

Colombia, Argentina and Chile), Africa (South Africa, Morocco, Egypt, Kenya and more), Russia, China, India, Japan, Australia and several countries in the middle East. The ten most active countries are listed in Table 1.

Figure 4: Map showing which countries have accessed the ACINO web site (from Google analytics).

Table 1: List of the 10 countries that created the highest number of sessions with the ACINO web site (from Google analytics).

Country	Sessions (total: 3462)	New users (total 3123)
United States	890	872
(not set)	855	855
China	178	174
Italy	151	66
Japan	134	134
Russia	121	49
Sweden	108	62
Germany	100	88
United Kingdom	84	80
Spain	73	44

2.1.3 Twitter account

We have opened the twitter account **@acinoH2020** [ACITWIT] to raise awareness about the project, create a community of stakeholders and future adopters, and hopefully improve the visibility of the results. Twitter is an ideal tool to publish ephemeral information about events, and our main focus has been on Software-Defined Network (SDN) events as well as ACINO's own meetings. As of January 2016, there have been approximately 50 tweets, and the account has 49 followers.

2.1.4 Fact sheet and flyer

To help support our communication in conferences and workshops, we have designed a fact sheet and a flyer for the project. The fact sheet, shown in Figure 5, provides the reader with the main facts about the projects: the project administrative side, with the list of partners, duration, cost and European grant number are clearly stated. Contact details (to the project coordinator, links to the project web site and twitter account) are provided. The project context, motivation and main objective are presented, the concept and technical approach are briefly discussed and the key issues that the project is targeting are listed, along with the expected impact.

The flyer, shown in Figure 6, is a short technical introduction to the project: it provides on one side of the flyer the project name and title, contact details and the list of the project partners. The other side of the flyer is a short technical description of the project goals.

Figure 5: Pictures of the two-page ACINO fact sheet.

The **ACINO project** is a small scale project under the EU Horizon 2020 Programme, ICT6 - smart optical and wireless network technologies. The ACINO project started in February 2015 and will continue until January 2018.

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ACINO

Application-Centric IP/ Optical Network Orchestration

The ACINO consortium

This project is funded by the European Union

ACINO

Application-Centric IP/Optical Network Orchestration

The Application Centric IP/ Optical Network Orchestration (ACINO) project aims to offer tailored services to business applications by operating the transport infrastructure in a more programmable and dynamic way. This will allow application and network solution providers to transfer and protect large amounts of data more effectively, by executing operations initiated by the applications themselves. Such traffic can originate from 5G networks, be generated by business applications that migrate virtual machines or backup data, or contain content from video-on-demand and TV broadcasting.

ACINO proposes the application-centric concept, in which the requirements of the traffic of each application are met by exploiting the different features of the IP and optical layers, thus resulting in high-performance, customized services. To this end, ACINO develops a Software-Defined-Network-based (SDN) orchestrator capable of managing the transport segments of the core and backbone telecommunication networks.

Expected Impacts

- Enable IP and optical layer services directly satisfying the application needs;
- Prove the value of dynamic and elastic optical technologies;
- Tackle the lack of dynamic control of transport networks by means of automated SDN-based multi-layer resource orchestration;
- Reduce energy consumption by bypassing the grooming layer;
- Foster the emergence of open industry with an open source and vendor-agnostic approach.

Expected Results – An open source modular orchestrator enabling applications to program the IP/Optical transport network by means of high-level primitives.

Figure 6: Pictures of the two-page ACINO flyer.

2.2 Communications

During the first year of the project, we have had two communication actions: a press release and an interview in a magazine:

- **March 2015:** On 03/02/2015, CREATE-NET posted on its website a short article introducing the project and highlighting the main benefits for the operators and users adopting the proposed

technology. The post has been produced both in English and Italian languages; the English version is available at [NCRE].

- **May 2015:** On May 10, 2015, Ioannis Tomkos from AIT was interviewed by the Gazzetabyte online magazine for an article on the topic “Optical networking: The next 10 years”, in which he also introduced the ACINO project. The article can be found at [TOMGAZ].

3 Dissemination activities

During this first year, the consortium has published four articles in conferences. Four presentations have also been held at conferences. We participated to the organization of a workshop, held a course and a tutorial. We held booths at three conferences and ran demonstrations in them. These activities are detailed below.

3.1 Scientific publications in conferences

3.1.1 Application-centric networks and the future 5G transport

This article [SKOICT] was written by Pontus Sköldström and Stéphane Junique (Acreo) and published at the **International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON) [ICTON2015]** in June 2015.

The article presents the Application-centric IP/Optical network concept pursued by the H2020 project ACINO, and how it could be applied as a future 5G transport network. While 5G concepts are still maturing, the article investigates the envisioned capabilities of a 5G network, the use-cases and the requirements different applications would have on a wired transport network for 5G. Our conclusion is that ACINO could fulfill the bandwidth, low-latency, security, and reliability requirements, in a way that differentiates between different 5G services.

3.1.2 The need for SDN in Orchestration of IP over Optical MultiVendor

This article [GERECOC] was written by Ori Gerstel (Sedona) and Victor Lopez (Telefonica) and published at the **European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC) [ECOC]** in September 2015.

The article explains why distributed control lacks the ability to optimally control networks with multiple transport domains or both IP and optical layers. We then propose a practical architecture to fix these issues and experimentally demonstrate it over commercial IP/transport gear.

3.1.3 Multi-layer orchestration for application-centric networking

This article [GERPIS] was written by Ori Gerstel (Sedona), Victor Lopez (Telefonica) and Domenico Siracusa (CREATE-NET) and published in **Photonics in Switching [PIS]** in September, 2015.

The article argues that the implementation of services in an IP-optical network should be driven by the needs of the specific applications, and explains why this requires a centralized orchestration architecture.

3.1.4 Optical Network Programmability - Requirements and Applications

This article [AUTPIS] was written by Achim Autenrieth (ADVA), Jörg Peter Elbers (ADVA), Thomas Szyrkowicz (ADVA & TU Munich), Pawel Kaczmarek (ADVA), Wolfgang Kellerer (TU Munich) and published in **Photonics in Switching [PIS]** in September, 2015.

The article describes the requirements, applications and use cases for optical network programmability. Based on application scenarios, open northbound Application Programme Interfaces (APIs) with different levels of control and abstraction to address different network operator requirements are defined. For their illustration, use cases for optical network programmability show current research directions.

3.2 Workshop organisation

Domenico Siracusa (CREATE-NET) has participated to the organization of the **Workshop on Network Function Virtualization and Programmable Networks** that was part of the European Conference on Networks and Communications (EUCNC) held in June 2015. The program of the Workshop is available at [EUCNC].

3.3 Presentations at conferences

3.3.1 ACINO: Application Centric IP/Optical Network Orchestration

Domenico Siracusa (CREATE-NET) held a presentation [SIREU] during the workshop on **Network Function Virtualization and Programmable Networks** (see paragraph 3.2) introducing the main concepts of the ACINO project and discussing the topic of the network programmability applied in the context of transport networks.

3.3.2 Control and Orchestration for Future IP/Optical Transport Networks

Domenico Siracusa (CREATE-NET) has given a presentation [SIRPND] at the **Photonic Networks and Devices 2015** held within the OSA Advanced Photonics Conference, held in June 2015.

The presentation addressed next-generation transport networks (also based on novel technologies such as Space Division Multiplexing and their interaction with the advanced applications, which are demanding very high capacities for tailored services. In this context, the ACINO approach to network orchestration has been discussed.

3.3.3 Resource Management in 5G Transport Networks

Domenico Siracusa (CREATE-NET) has given a presentation [SIRCTTE] at the **Workshop on Convergence of fixed and mobile broadband networks** organized within the Conference of Telecommunication, Media and Internet Techno-Economics (CTTE), held in November 2015.

The presentation promoted the concept of an adaptive and sharable 5G transport network solution integrating the fronthaul and backhaul segments of the network (the so called Xhaul). In addition, it stressed the need to fulfil applications' requirements on an end-to-end basis, by proposing a study-case that includes the metro/core transport segments and highlights the possible interaction between the Xhaul control solution and the multi-layer/multi-technology orchestrator for transport networks that is proposed in ACINO.

3.3.4 Adding application awareness in flexible optical networking

Dimitrios Klonidis from AIT gave a presentation [APPAW] at the **i-Can workshop on Information-Centric Access Networks [ICAN]** that took place at the Athens University of Economics and Business in Athens, Greece on 2-3 June 2015. The presentation introduced the ACINO concept.

3.4 Courses and tutorials held

SEDONA Systems were present at the Optical Fiber Conference (OFC). Ori Gerstel provided a tutorial entitled "Control Architectures for Multi-layer Networking: Distributed, centralized, or something in between?" in which he reviewed the spectrum of likely centralized and distributed control architectures

and explain how different use cases will shape the optimal choice. The conclusion was that practical considerations dictate that network control will not be fully centralized – even in the SDN era.

Ori Gerstel also provided a 3 hour long course entitled: “SC411: Multi-layer Interaction in the Age of Agile Optical Networking”, in which he provided an overview of multi-layer networking – including physical integration and control plane integration between the layers. He then described the different use cases for multi-layer control and the value that each of them brings to the network operator.

3.5 Attended events

3.5.1 Demonstration and tutorials at the Optical Fiber Conference (OFC)

SEDONA Systems were present at the Optical Fiber Conference (OFC), as mentioned in section 3.4. In addition to the tutorial and course that they held, they hosted a booth in which they demonstrated early feasibility of multi-layer control over commercial optical and IP gear in the lab of Telefonica. The demonstration showed the ability to interface with multiple controllers for different domains, and the ability to present a unified view of the network and to optimize the IP layer based on changing traffic conditions.

3.5.2 Demonstration at the SDN & OpenFlow World Congress

SEDONA Systems has hosted a booth at the SDN & OpenFlow World Congress [SDNWC] where the company vision on the topic of multi-layer orchestration has been proposed and discussed and an implementation of architecture, as well as several important applications, has been demonstrated. In addition to that, the booth exposed the project flyers (see Section 2.1.4 Fact sheet), which have been discussed with the interested congress attendees.

CREATE-NET has also attended the congress and promoted the project concepts thanks to the support of the flyers. The congress has been an interesting opportunity to share ideas and receive the interest of many companies operating in the field of transport networks (e.g. Deutsche Telekom, KT, and others).

3.5.3 Demonstration at the Open Networking Symposium (ONS)

SEDONA Systems has hosted a booth at the ONS in Santa Clara, CA [ONS], in which it demonstrated the basic capabilities that are needed for multi-layer control, such as the ability automatically detect how the IP layer and optical layer are connected.

4 Participation in open Source Software communities

4.1 Telefonica Netphony Controller

4.1.1 What is the Netphony controller

The Telefonica Netphony suite is a set of java based libraries that enable to create a PCE/GMPLS/ABNO based control plane. It comprises a set of components, distributed as jar files, which are hosted in publicly available github repositories.

This ABNO repository contains a reference implementation of the ABNO controller. In order to run the ABNOController implementation, there is a set of pre-requisites:

1. A PCE has to be running and listening before the ABNO Controller is started [NETPCE]. Otherwise, if there isn't a PCE listening for new sessions, the controller will shut down.
2. To start ABNOController it is required to configure the ABNO parameters (ports with the rest of the modules).

4.1.2 Relevance of Netphony for ACINO

The Netphony suite is relevant for ACINO as it will provide an emulated environment for GMPLS/PCE networks with Wavelength Switched Optical Networks (WSON) and Spectrum Switched Optical Networks (SSON). The Netphony suite supports PCEP features (RFC 5440, RFC 5521 (partial), RFC 5886, RFC 6006 (partial), draft-ietf-pce-gmpls-pcep-extensions-10 (partial), draft-ietf-pce-inter-layer-ext-05 (partial), draft-ietf-pce-hierarchy-extensions-02, draft-ietf-pce-stateful-pce-05, draft-ietf-pce-pcep-stateful-pce-gmpls-00 and draft-ietf-pce-pce-initiated-lsp-00. Regarding, RSVP (Resource ReSerVation Protocol) it implements RFC 3209. OSPF (Open Shortest Path First) support includes OSPF-TE v2 LSA from RFC3630 and Inter-AS-TE-v2 LSA from RFC5392. Finally BGP-LS (Border Gateway Protocol – Link State) support includes draft-ietf-idr-ls-distribution-03.

Previous protocols enables to have an scenario where the network elements disseminates the topology to the PCE using OSPF, while the PCE can provision services through PCEP to the network elements, which propagates the path using RSVP. Finally, the PCE can export the topology using BGP/LS to any other controller. The ABNO controller orchestrates the services and the interaction for multi-layer or multi-domain scenarios.

4.1.3 ACINO's contribution to the project

The contribution to this open source project has been the improvement on the documentation and bug fixing based on the feedback from the partners and the demo done internally to validate its utilization in the consortium.

4.2 ONOS (Open Network Operating System)

4.2.1 What is the ONOS controller

ONOS is an open source SDN network operating system, architected to provide a resilient, high performance SDN control plane featuring northbound (Intent Framework) and southbound (OpenFlow,

NETConf, OVSDb, ...) abstractions and interfaces for a diversity of management, control, service applications and network devices. Since October 2015, ONOS and Linux Foundation established a strategic partnership to create open source SDN and NFV platforms and solutions.

4.2.2 Relevance of ONOS for ACINO

As mentioned in ACINO deliverable D3.1 [D31], ONOS has been selected as the framework for the development of the ACINO orchestrator, since it has been evaluated to be the solution that better matches the requirements of the project. Furthermore, Milestone 21 [MS21] has described the ONOS packet-optical use-case, which already addresses a subset of the multi-layer networking issues that are relevant for the ACINO project.

ONOS is a multi-module project whose modules are managed as OSGi bundles inside an Apache Karaf framework. ACINO Applications can interact with ONOS through the Intent Framework that allows specifying their network control desires in form of policy rather than mechanism. The ONOS core accepts the intent specifications and translates them into device-specific operations (e.g. OpenFlow rules, NETCONF YANG configuration, etc.).

The converged solution proposed in the ONOS packet-optical use-case does not share the same application-centric vision of ACINO and provides a basic implementation (based on OpenFlow) that can be used as the initial building block for the WP4 activities. This Work Package will aim at improving the existing solution according to the main technical directions of the project.

4.2.3 ACINO's contribution to the project

The contribution of ACINO to the ONOS community is still at an early stage and under discussion. However, despite the selection of ONOS as the reference development framework is quite recent, the project has initiated a close interaction with the community. More specifically:

- The ACINO concepts, the possible enhancements and contributions that the project activities can provide to ONOS have been presented by Domenico Siracusa (CREATE-NET) at the ONOS Technical Steering Team (TST) meeting of the 27/01/2016. The TSC [ONTST] is responsible for all technical decisions in the project. They are responsible for the content and structure of the code base and for all technical priorities with respect to the code base. The ONOS chief architect is the team lead of the technical steering team.
- Domenico Siracusa (CREATE-NET) is getting involved in the ONOS Community Steering Team [ONCST], which is a very young team responsible for the care and feeding of the community.

4.3 Net2plan

4.3.1 What is Net2Plan

Net2Plan [NET2PLAN] is an open source network planner and optimizer. It uses an abstract, multi-layer network representation, which makes it technology agnostic. User-define attributes can be added to network components, making it very flexible.

Net2Plan is written in Java and published under the Lesser GNU General Public License [LGPL], a license that should be flexible enough for the project needs.

4.3.2 Relevance of Net2Plan for ACINO

The network optimizer in ONOS is quite simplistic and seems to be code-wise not separate from the intent compiler. ACINO may need a new network planner. Net2Plan is multi-layer-aware and its network model is extensible: these are strong arguments in favour of considering it as the base for ACINO's network optimizer.

Net2Plan also contains a network planner. One of ACINO's goals is to develop an online network planner, to re-optimize the network using new constraints or to foresee the consequence of events such as maintenance or hardware downs. Having the same piece of software to provide both optimization and planning capabilities would be an added advantage in terms of development time and amount of code to become familiar with.

Finally, both ONOS and Net2Plan are written in Java, which again should make the development easier.

4.3.3 ACINO's contribution to the project

The contacts between ACINO and the Net2Plan author are still at an early stage and under discussion. The project plans to discuss with the Net2Lab author how to implement ACINO's features so they integrate as smoothly as possible with the software and present a value to the Net2Lab author.

5 Planned activities for the second year

5.1 Organization of workshops

In order to increase the visibility of the project and create a community around the ACINO concepts, the project has planned the organization of a workshop for its second year (thus achieving MS33).

These plans have already materialised as ACINO will organise the first **Workshop on Multi-Layer Network Orchestration** (NetOrch), co-located with the 18th International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2016) [ICTON2016] which will be held in July 2016, in Trento. The conference has a good attendance in terms of participants (on average, more than 350) and the technical co-sponsorship by the IEEE Photonics Society is foreseen.

The scope of the workshop is to create an international table of discussion where researchers and enthusiasts of network control and management are invited to contribute on the topic of multi-layer orchestration and programmability for future converged packet/circuit networks. Application-aware networking and inter data center communications are also mentioned among the topics of interest.

In addition, the project is submitting a workshop proposal at the EUCNC, together with European projects NEPHELE and COSIGN. The three projects are performing complementary research on data center networking and propose this joint effort in order provide a workshop with a broad scope and attract leading scientists in the field, on a global scale.

5.2 Planned publications and participation in conferences

The project regularly updates a list of conferences of interest to allow its members to plan ahead paper submissions and conference attendance. The current list of events for 2016 is shown in Table 2.

Several scientific journals can be targeted for publication of results. The main ones that we have identified corresponding to the research field of ACINO are:

- IEEE/OSA Journal of Lightwave Technologies
- IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking
- IEEE Communications Magazine
- IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking
- IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications
- IEEE Network
- Elsevier Journal of Optical Switching and Networking
- IEEE Transactions on Communications
- IEEE Proceedings
- Elsevier Computer Networks

Table 2: List of events of interest to ACINO members taking place in 2016. The second column indicates the deadline to submit a paper; the third and fourth columns provide the event date.

Event name and location	Submission deadline	Event Start Date	Event End Date	Link to event
Open Networking Summit, Santa Clara, California		2016-03-14	2016-03-17	http://opennetsummit.org/
OFC 2016, Anaheim, California	2016-03-07	2016-03-20	2016-03-24	http://www.ofcconference.org/en-us/home/
ONDM, Cartagena, Spain	2016-02-14	2016-05-09	2016-05-12	http://ondm2016.upct.es/cfp.php
NOC, Lisbon, Portugal		2016-06-01	2016-06-03	http://noc2016.iscte-iul.pt/
EUCNC, Athens, Greece	2016-02-26	2016-06-27	2016-06-30	http://www.eucnc.eu/
Next-gen optical networking, Nice, France		2016-06-28	2016-07-01	http://nextgenerationoptical.com/
ICTON 2016, Trento, Italy	2016-03-31	2016-07-10	2016-07-14	https://icton2016.fbk.eu/
ECOC 2016, Düsseldorf, Germany	2016-04-22	2016-09-18	2016-09-22	http://www.ecocexhibition.com http://www.ecoc2016.de
EWSDN, Bilbao, Spain	2016-06-17	2016-09-30	2016-10-02	http://www.ewsdn.eu/
SDN congress 2016, The Hague, Netherlands		2016-10-11	2016-10-14	http://www.layer123.com/sdn
Globecom, Washington DC	2016-04-01	2016-12-04	2016-12-08	http://globecom2016.ieee-globecom.org/
INFOCOM 2017, San Francisco, California	July 2016	2017-04-01	2017-04-01	www.ieee-infocom.org
ICC 2017, France	September 2016	2017-05-21	2017-05-25	http://www.ieee-icc.org/
OFC 2017, USA	October 2016	2017-03-19	2017-03-23	http://www.ofcconference.org/en-us/home/about/future-dates/

5.3 Contacts with other projects and forums

Project ACINO will pursue interactions with other projects as well as national and worldwide forums for the effective dissemination of the project results and the cross-fertilization of ideas and concepts. The liaison with other related national and international research activities will be pursued as a normal operational practice.

During the first period, the ACINO project has identified concrete opportunities for liaison with relevant projects and forums, for diverse purposes, which includes joint dissemination actions, technological exchanges, joint open source development actions etc. Most of these liaison actions are currently being followed up and are at various stages of development. In particular, the following list of liaison are currently being explored:

- **H2020 5G-CROSSHAUL:** the 5G-CROSSHAUL project [5GCRO] aims at developing a 5G integrated backhaul and fronthaul transport network. Common partners to both projects have identified the potential for a joint use-case in which an application-aware end-to-end service is provided. Therefore, the liaison with 5G-CROSSHAUL is currently exploring the possibility to create this case and demonstrate it; furthermore, the two projects are also identifying joint-dissemination events.
- **USA-JPN ACTION (JUNO program):** the ACTION project [ACTION] enables adaptation of the Internet to changing needs and demands by dynamically adjusting its “optical highway” capacities based on network resource utilization. Given the similar scope of the two projects, contacts have been established in order to setup collaborations in terms of cross-project investigations, with the aim of targeting joint-dissemination events.
- **H2020 NEPHELE:** the NEPHELE project [NEPHELE] is developing a dynamic optical network infrastructure for future scale-out, disaggregated data centers. The two projects have identified a possible collaboration related with the management of services between data centers. Within the H2020 cluster and concertation activities, the liaison with NEPHELE is expected on joint dissemination and communication actions, in particular, to explore joint workshops/sessions at EU-level conferences (e.g. EUCNC).
- **FP7 COSIGN:** the COSIGN project [COSIGN] aims at defining and implementing a flat, scalable Data-Centre-Network architecture, empowered by novel optical technologies and SDN based network control. As for the NEPHELE project, the liaison with COSIGN can explore the networking aspects between data centers. The two projects are also evaluating possible joint dissemination and communication actions (e.g. EUCNC).
- **H2020 VITAL:** the VITAL project [VITAL] is investigating multi-domain service orchestration in the context of satellite and terrestrial networks. Liaison with ACINO is currently explored in order to organize joint dissemination events surrounding multi-layer/multi-domain network service orchestration. CREATE-NET is coordinating the VITAL project and will be in charge of expediting this effort.
- **FP7 INSPACE:** the INSPACE project [INSPACE] is working on the introduction of the Space Division Multiplexing paradigm in optical networks. The common partners among the two projects are

investigating how INSPACE activities can feed ACINO (especially the ones related with the spectral and spatial flexibility of the optical layer and the software-defined control of the optical network).

- **FP7 EU-JPN STRAUSS:** the STRAUSS project [STRAUSS] aims at defining a highly efficient and global (multi-domain) optical infrastructure for Ethernet transport. In particular, it developed a Control Orchestration Protocol (COP), i.e., a subset of the T-API defined by ONF, which can be re-used in ACINO to enable the communication between the orchestrator and the controllers. The common partners among the two projects are evaluating this possibility.

In addition to these research projects, the ACINO consortium is constantly interacting with other communities, such as the ONOS and Net2Plan ones, as has been described in Section 4.

The ACINO project has also requested for cooperation with the 5G-PPP initiative in order to present the ACINO scenarios and architecture within the framework of 5G Architecture developments. This process was initiated by the EC during the consultation for the H2020 ICT cluster re-organization discussion, and ACINO project has provided its interest. More discussions and decisions are expected to take place during the concertation meeting at Brussels, during March 2016.

5.4 Participation to EC-sponsored events

Unit E.1 (Network Technologies), within Directorate E (Net Futures), supports research activities on wireless, optical & satellite communication technologies that can cope with the massive projected increases in network traffic. The goal is to reinforce European industry in the global communication markets through leadership in innovative network technologies (optical, wireless, satellite) and systems.

In order to support these activities and enforce the achievement of the objectives, different events are organized. The ACINO project, as part of the project portfolio, is committed to actively participate and contribute to these events, fostering the aggregation of the project work in the unified framework of related European projects.

The first event in the agenda is the FP7 and H2020 Network Technologies Concertation Day, which will take place in Brussels on March 1st. The event will focus on information and coordination of the running FP7 and H2020 projects from call ICT5 and ICT6, and it will be a table of discussion for the interaction with the 5G-PPP community. ACINO will attend this event and participate to the Converged and Optical Networks (CaON) Cluster dedicated meeting.

6 Conclusion

ACINO has had a very active first year in communication and dissemination: A dissemination strategy has been devised, defining the key goals, targets and means of communication.

Generic communication instrument have been designed: a graphical profile, document templates, a web site, a twitter account, a fact sheet and a flyer. Statistics of the web site show that it has attracted visitors from all continents. Two communication actions have taken place, a press release and an interview in a magazine.

Dissemination has been prolific, with fifteen unique activities, including articles and presentations at conferences, demonstrations at conference booths, tutorials and courses, and the contribution to an open source project. Furthermore, ACINO has planned the workshop for the second year of the project.

Finally, the project has devised detailed plans for its dissemination activities for the coming year.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programme Interface
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol
BGP/LS	Border Gateway Protocol/LinkState
COP	Control Orchestration Protocol
CTTE	Conference of Telecommunication, Media and Internet Techno-Economics
ECOC	European Conference on Optical Communication
EUCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
GMPLS	Generalised Multiprotocol Label Switching
ICTON	International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
KT	Telecommunications company in South Korea, formerly Korea Telecom
NETCONF	The Network Configuration Protocol
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
ONF	Open Networking Foundation
ONS	Open Network Symposium
OSGi	Open Services Gateway initiative
OSPF	Open Shortest Path First
OSS	Open Source Software
OVSDB	Open vSwitch Database
PCE	Path Computation Element
PCEP	Path Computation Element Protocol

PIS	Photonics in Switching
RFC	Request For Comments
RSVP	Resource ReSerVation Protocol
SDN	Software-Defined Network
SSON	Spectrum Switched Optical Networks
T-API	Transport-API
TST	The ONOS Technical Steering Team
WSO	WaveLength Switched Optical Networks
YANG	The “Yet Another Next Generation” data modelling language

7 References

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[ACITWIT]	ACINO twitter account: https://twitter.com/acinoH2020
[ACIWEB]	ACINO website: http://www.acino.eu
[ACTION]	ACTION project: http://venividiwiki.ee.virginia.edu/mediawiki/index.php/ACTION
[APPAW]	Presentation “Adding application awareness in flexible optical networking”: http://mm.aueb.gr/i-can/workshop/index.php
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[GERECO]	O. Gerstel, V. Lopez, “The need for SDN in orchestration of IP over optical multi-vendor networks”, European Conference on Optical Communication, pp. 1-3 (2015).
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[ICAN]	i-Can workshop on Information-Centric Access Networks: http://mm.aueb.gr/i-can/workshop/index.php
[ICTON2015]	ICTON conference site (2015): http://www.icton2015.hu
[ICTON2016]	International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks: https://icton2016.fbk.eu/
[INSPACE]	INSPACE project: http://www.ict-inspace.eu
[MS21]	ACINO milestone 21, "Emulator Environment", 2016.
[NCRE]	Press release from CREATE-NET on 03/02/2015: http://www.create-net.org/news/trentino-ready-face-challenges-set-h2020

[NEPHELE]	NEPHELE project: www.nepheleproject.eu
[NET2PLAN]	Net2Plan project: http://net2plan.com
[NETPCE]	Netphony PCE: https://github.com/telefonicaid/netphony-pce
[ONS]	Open Net Summit 2015: http://opennetsummit.org/2015-archive
[ONCST]	ONOS Community Steering Team: https://wiki.onosproject.org/display/ONOSST/Community+Steering+Team
[ONTST]	ONOS Technical Steering Team: https://wiki.onosproject.org/display/ONOSST/Technical+Steering+Team
[PIS]	Photonics in Switching conference site (2015): http://www.ps2015.com
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[VITAL]	VITAL project: http://www.ict-vital.eu